

Steric Effects on the Pyridinium Fluorochromate Oxidation of some Substituted Piperidin-4-ones

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Kinetics of oxidation of 3-alkyl- and 3,5-dimethyl-substituted-1-methyl-2,6-diphenylpiperidin-4-ones by pyridinium fluorochromate (PFC) in aqueous acetic acid (50%, v/v) at fixed $[H_2SO_4]$ have been carried out iodometrically under pseudo first order conditions in the temperature range 35–50°. The reaction is found to be first order each with respect to [piperidone] and [PFC]. The rate increases with increase in $[H^+]$ and solvent composition (AcOH) in the reaction mixture. Activation energies and related thermodynamic parameters have been determined and compared. A plausible mechanism rationalising the observed kinetic data is proposed. The structural effects are discussed on the basis of conformation.

The kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of 4-piperidones by a few well-known oxidants like $KMnO_4$ ¹, CrO_3 ², vanadium(v)³ and cerium(IV)⁴ have been investigated. Pyridinium fluorochromate is a recently developed oxidant. Its limited exposure in the kinetics of oxidation prompted us to undertake the present investigation.

Results and Discussion

All the experiments were carried out under pseudo-first order conditions. Plots of $\log [PFC]$ vs time were found to be linear upto 50% conversion of PFC with 1-methyl, 3-methylpiperidin-4-one as substrate (Fig. 1). All the other 1-methylpiperidones

showed similar behaviour. Contrary to expectations, at constant piperidone and H^+ concentrations, k_{obs} was found to decrease with increase in [PFC]. The values of k_{obs} at different initial concentrations of piperidones and at fixed concentrations of PFC and H^+ were found to depend linearly on [piperidone]. Plots of k_{obs} vs [piperidone] were found to be linear and to pass through the origin (Fig. 2).

Fig. 1. Plots of $\log [PFC]$ vs time.

Fig. 2. Plots of k_{obs} vs [Piperidone].

This shows that at constant $[H^+]$, the rate equation can be written as

$$\frac{-d[PFC]}{dt} = k_2 [PFC] [\text{piperidone}] = k_{obs} [PFC]$$

where $k_{obs} = k_2 [\text{piperidone}]$. From the plots of k_{obs} vs $[\text{piperidone}]$, the second order rate constants were evaluated (Table 1).

TABLE 1—SECOND ORDER RATE CONSTANTS FOR THE PFC-OXIDATION OF 3- AND 3,5-SUBSTITUTED-2,6-DIPHENYLPYPERIDIN-4-ONES

Aq. HOAc=50% (v/v), $[H_2SO_4]=0.625 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$
 $[PFC]=1.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$

Sl. no.	Substrate	$k_2 \times 10^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$
1.	1-Methyl-3-ethyl	4.33
2.	1-Methyl-3-methyl	3.50
3.	1-Methyl-3-isopropyl	2.83
4.	1-Methyl-3-H	1.16
5.	1,3,5-Trimethyl	0.49
6.	1-Methyl-3,3-dimethyl	0.28

The values of k_{obs} were found to increase with increase in $[H^+]$ suggesting that the reactions are acid-catalysed and the plots of k_{obs} vs $[H^+]$ were found to be linear with almost unit slope and a positive intercept indicating the occurrence of acid-dependent and acid-independent processes concurrently. This leads to the rate law expression,

$$\frac{-d[PFC]}{dt} = k_a [PFC] [\text{piperidone}] [H^+] + k_b [PFC] [\text{piperidone}]$$

where k_a and k_b are the acid-dependent and acid-independent rate constants respectively.

A change in ionic strength over 2.025–3.937 M showed no pronounced effect on the k_{obs} value. The increase in percentage of acetic acid accelerated the rate of oxidation. This may probably be due to the ion-dipole interaction of the reactants⁶, which was confirmed by a linear plot of $\log k_{obs}$ vs $1/D$. The reactions were studied at four different temperatures and from the temperature dependence of k_{obs} , the activation parameters were calculated (Table 2)

TABLE 2—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR THE OXIDATION OF 3-SUBSTITUTED-1-METHYL-2,6-DIPHENYLPYPERIDIN-4-ONES BY PFC AT 318 K

Piperidones	E_a kJ mol ⁻¹	$\Delta H^\ddagger$ kJ mol ⁻¹	$\Delta G^\ddagger$ kJ mol ⁻¹	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
3-Ethyl	58.9	56.3	86.3	94.4
3-Methyl	72.9	70.2	86.9	52.5
3-Isopropyl	66.8	64.2	87.5	73.2
3-H	70.2	67.6	89.8	70.0
3,5-Dimethyl	83.1	80.4	92.1	36.7
3,3-Dimethyl	94.4	91.8	93.5	5.6

while the energy of activation indicates the order of reactivity among the piperidones, the existence of a linear relationship between $\Delta H^\ddagger$ and $\Delta S^\ddagger$

indicates that a single mechanism is operating throughout the series.

The scavenger methyl methacrylate failed to induce polymerisation indicating the absence of free radicals during the course of oxidation.

Comparison of rate of attack of oxidant on piperidones furnishes information regarding the steric environment and hence their conformations. The rate constant sequence observed is $k_{ethyl} > k_{methyl} > k_{isopropyl} > k_H > k_{3,5\text{-dimethyl}} > k_{3,3\text{-dimethyl}}$. The 3-alkyl-substituted-1-hetero-4-cyclohexanols have shown to exist in the anchored chair form with the alkyl and phenyl groups in the most stable equatorial position⁶. The same can be expected in 3-alkyl-1-hetero-4-piperidones.

The PFC oxidation relieves the non-bonded steric interactions of the vicinal alkyl group and hence a 3-alkyl substituent enhances the rate. The observed rate constant sequence indicates that Me-OH non-bonded interaction is essential in the oxidation of the molecule. This interaction is greater in 3-ethyl than in 3-methyl due to its larger size, resulting in higher reactivity. Irrespective of the larger size, 3-isopropyl has a low rate. This may be due to the lowering of the essential Me-OH interaction by the Ph-Me interactions present in two of its three conformations in the equilibrium mixture. This interaction may result in the distortion of the chair conformation. The rate constant of 3,5-dimethyl-1-methyl-2,6-diphenylpiperidin-4-one is significantly less suggesting a non-chair conformation. Since in a non-chair conformation the Me-OH interaction is relieved in the ground state itself, the 3,5-dimethylpiperidone undergoes a slower oxidation. In this oxidation, 3,3-dimethyl is found to be the least reactive. The presence of two methyl groups on the adjacent carbon atom of the reaction centre has a hindering effect due to distorted chair conformation.

The probable mechanism given in Scheme 1 is in consistent with the kinetic data.

The stoichiometry 1 : 3 and the main product a dicarboxylic acid analysed and characterised, substantiate the above mechanism.

Experimental

PFC is a complex of chromium trioxide, pyridine and hydrofluoric acid and was prepared by the reported method⁷.

The substituted piperidin-4-ones were prepared and purified⁸. Glacial acetic acid unaffected by

chromic acid was used as such. All the reagents used were of analytical grade. Conductivity water used in preparing all solutions. Substrate and oxidant solutions were prepared afresh. The pseudo-first order condition was maintained by keeping the substrate and acid concentrations always in excess over that of PFC. The rates of oxidation were measured in 50% (v/v) acetic acid following the disappearance of the oxidant by iodometry, for 50% utilisation of the oxidant, and the results were found to be reproducible within $\pm 2\%$ deviation.

The stoichiometry of the reactions were determined by allowing a known excess of the oxidant PFC to react with the substrates in presence of H_2SO_4 in aqueous acid medium and estimating the unreacted PFC after completion of the reaction. The formation of dicarboxylic acid was detected and characterised by tlc, ir, nmr and systematic qualitative tests.

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